

COMPRESSION-COMPRESSION FATIGUE OF GLASS-FIBRE NON-CRIMP FABRIC COMPOSITES BY FOUR-POINT FLEXURE

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INTRODUCTION: COMPRESSION FATIGUE

Important but often neglected load case.

Lacking in standardised guidance for testing and specimen design.

Simple end- or shear-loading tests may not meet requirements:

- Global buckling instability
- Short gauge length
- End crushing
- Stress concentrations at tabs or grips

Four-point bending provides a promising alternative.

End Loading

Shear Loading

Combined Loading

Bending Loading

INTRODUCTION: STITCHED FABRICS

'Pattern' refers to the geometry or weave-type of the stitching thread

Can influence fibre alignment:

- key for static compression behaviour
- May also play a influence compression-compression fatigue

Characteristic	Stitch Pattern		
	Chain	Tricot	Mixed
Fabric areal weight, reported (gsm)	820	825	825
Fabric areal weight, measured (gsm)	828	803	815
Fabric as-manufactured fibre orientation (°)	[+45/-45]	[0/90]	[0/90]
Stitch thread linear density (dtex)	84.5	107	108
Stitch gauge (mm)	5.15	3.99	4.30
Stitch length (mm)	2.57	6.94 (3.47)	14.84 (3.71)

- 1) Develop a specimen geometry to test stitched glass-fibre fabrics in compression-compression fatigue
- 2) Determine if fatigue behaviour varies between fabrics with different stitching patterns
- 3) Determine whether this variation can be linked to the previously-measured variation in fibre misalignment

SPECIMEN DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE

Asymmetric sandwich based on ASTM D5467 for static compression

Maximum compression strains up to 1.5%

Compression facesheet strain gradient 3.95%

Identical rear (tension) facesheets

50 mm gauge length

TEST APPARATUS AND PROCEDURE

Controlled sinusoidal
displacements at 0.5 Hz

Continuous load / displacement
measurement

Direct strain measurement for
first 150 cycles

Minimum displacement 5 mm,
Maximum displacements 25, 30,
35, 40 or 45 mm

Maximum compressive strains
0.85 – 1.5%

Run-out at 10,000 cycles

BEAM LOAD AND STIFFNESS

'Stiffness' contains both flexural rigidity (EI) and transverse shear stiffness
Transverse load and stiffness change over time, possibly due to:

- Change in core shear stiffness
- Change in facesheet stiffnesses (tension, compression, or both)
- Permanent core deformation

Linear regression of the form:

$$\log(S) = \log(A) + B \log(N)$$

A: Intercept. Strain for a fatigue life of 1 cycle, i.e. predicted static strain

B: Slope

Run-out specimens excluded

High scatter results in flat fits with low R-squared

Fabric	A	B	R ²
Chain Front	1.87	-0.0538	0.578
Chain Rear	1.72	-0.0402	0.768
Tricot Front	1.87	-0.0428	0.526
Tricot Rear	1.46	-0.0117	0.0735
Mixed Front	1.81	-0.0614	0.661
Mixed Rear	1.46	-0.0474	0.575

VARIATION BETWEEN STITCH PATTERNS

Paired regression of the form:

$$S_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 P + (\beta_2 + \beta_3 P)N_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Tests whether changing P from 0 to 1 changes the intercept ($\beta_0 + \beta_1$) or slope ($\beta_2 + \beta_3$)

Statistically significant variation between the pair if $p < 0.05$

	C_F	C_R	T_F	T_R	M_F	M_R	
C_F	X	0.308	0.981	0.0371	0.780	0.0207	Intercept
C_R	0.318	X	0.435	0.0526	0.563	0.0272	
T_F	0.602	0.868	X	0.144	0.831	0.0939	
T_R	0.0315	0.0404	0.203	X	0.118	0.999	
M_F	0.697	0.150	0.393	0.0277	X	0.0759	
M_R	0.718	0.574	0.830	0.0471	0.477	X	
Slope							

FATIGUE LIFE EXPLAINED BY MISALIGNMENT

Weak positive relationship between intercept (A) and misalignment

Weak negative relationship between slope (B) and misalignment

Weak relationships are likely statistical artifacts due to the high scatter.

FAILURE AND DAMAGE

77.1% failed in compression within the gauge section. 18.1% survived to run-out

Visible 'whitening' observed in the top facesheet.

- Matrix damage?
- Interlaminar damage?
- Interfacial damage?
- Micro-cracking?

Inconsistent degrees of damage at failure

40 mm maximum displacement until failure

IMAGE ANALYSIS TO ISOLATE DAMAGE

Damage isolated from digital photographs

Morphological transformations identify and isolate:

- Damage created at the moment of failure
- Damage present before failure
- Other undesirable white reflections

DAMAGE RELATED TO FATIGUE SEVERITY

Fabric	A	B	R ²
Chain Front	0.203	0.345	0.274
Chain Rear	0.581	0.179	0.188
Tricot Front	0.0877	0.535	0.778
Tricot Rear	0.359	0.196	0.441
Mixed Front	0.742	0.299	0.486
Mixed Rear	3.18	0.0783	0.0399

Proposed relationship:

$$\log(D) = \log(A) + B \log(F)$$

D: Proportion of gauge area damaged

F: 'Fatigue severity', combining both applied strain and fatigue life:

$$F = N^S$$

Run-out specimens included

DAMAGE EXPLAINED BY MISALIGNMENT

Moderate positive relationship
between misalignment and damage
slope, B

Implies:

- More visible damage at the same fatigue severity
- Faster accumulation of damage under increasing fatigue severity (either strain or cycles)

Stronger relationship than between misalignment and fatigue life.

Four-point flexure was successful for testing in compression-compression fatigue, but scatter and variability are high

Failed specimens show visible whitening of the top facesheet, but exact damage mechanism requires further investigation

Weak relationships suggest higher misalignment may result in shorter fatigue lives and greater damage accumulation

Recommend further development to gather more repeatable data

THANK YOU

